

Identification of Biomarker Signatures and Candidate Drugs in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

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Abstract

Lung cancer is the most important health risk for human in worldwide. Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) is the most common cause of premature death from malignant disease. The aim of the study was to determine the pathways and expression profile of the genes to discover molecular signature at RNA and protein levels which could serve as potential drug targets for therapeutics innovation and the identification of novel targets. Eight proteins, six TFs and seven miRNAs came into prominence as potential drug targets. The differential expression profiles of these reporter biomolecules were cross-validated by independent RNA-Seq and miRNA-Seq. Risk discrimination performance of the reporter biomolecules NPR3, JUN, PPARG, TP53, CKMT1A, SP3 and TFAP2A were also evaluated. Total 213 drugs and 7 proteins was found for non-small cell lung cancer through dgidb. Among these identified drugs seven drugs such as- Gemcitabine, Carboplatin, paclitaxel, Docetaxel, Crizotinib, Bevacizumab and Gemcitabine is used for NSCLC which is approved by National Cancer Institute. The molecular signatures and repurposed drugs presented here permit further attention for experimental studies which are offer significant potential as biomarkers and candidate therapeutics for precision medicine approaches to clinical management of NSCLC.

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Introduction

Lung cancer is the second leading cause of cancer death worldwide among the human cancer. In Bangladesh, Lung cancers deaths reached 9,660 or 1.33% of total deaths according to the latest WHO data published in May, 2014. International Agency for Research on Cancer calculated cancer-related death rates in Bangladesh was 7.5% in 2005 and it will be 13% in 2030. Smoking, alcohol and high air pollutions are the main risk factor of lung cancer (Alberg *et al.*, 2013). Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) account for approximately 75% of all of lung cancers, which is the most common type of bronchial tumor in the world (Jemal *et al.*, 2007). Conventional diagnosis of lung cancer is currently based on tumor histology. The main histological types of NSCLC include adenocarcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, and large cell carcinoma. Despite the well-defined histological types of NSCLC, patient survival and treatment outcomes can differ substantially, even among NSCLCs of the same histological type and stage. Both sub-types adenocarcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma are very different in regard to copy number, DNA methylation, genetic mutations, transcriptome, proteome and biomarkers. Defining different lung cancer entities based on clinical, pathological and molecular alterations also determines disease evolution and treatment options. In spite of significant progress in the development of targeted-therapy, the high mortality rate in lung cancer firmly emphasizes the need for prevention and efficient detection of lung cancer, as well as a better classification, enabling patients to benefit from more specific therapy. Microarrays have been Lung cancer morphology exhibits a broad spectrum and many tumors are atypical or lack the morphologic features necessary for improved differential diagnoses. Lung cancer diagnoses based solely on morphological features are in many cases insufficient (D'Amico, 2008).

In recent years, there has been an expanding interest in the molecular genetic classification of cancers. Gene expression profiling is one of the methods used for this purpose. The data obtained from gene

expression analyses may allow the differentiation of cancer subgroups based on molecular phenotypes. Subgroups determined by gene expression in combination with clinical features like spread reflect the cancer's biology and progression better than histology alone (Golub, 2001).

The aim to reduce the high morbidity rate in lung cancer is related to growing efficiency of early detection and prevention of cancer risk factor strategies of lung cancer while still in a curable stage. Depend on the site of the primary tumor, these patient are treated with surgery and/or radiotherapy. Despite advances in early detection and standard treatment, NSCLC is often diagnosed at an advanced stage and carries a poor prognosis. Greater knowledge of the molecular origins and progression of lung cancer may lead to improvements in the treatment and prevention of the disease. Gene expression profiling offers a more functional molecular understanding of lung cancer that may grant insights into its pathophysiology and yield relevant information for staging, prognosis and therapeutic decision-making.

Microarrays have been used for more than two decades in pre-clinical research to determine gene-expression profiling associated with different pathological sub-groups or diverse clinical evolution and to evaluate biological and cellular functions determined by these gene panels. Improved outcomes for NSCLC are therefore clearly needed. There are a number of different strategies currently under evaluation. However, a better understanding of the molecular mechanisms that determine clinical outcomes is likely to provide the basis for more effective therapeutic intervention. Questions have been raised regarding the reproducibility of microarray result and there are examples of gene expression signature that even though validated in independent patient cohorts, show relative little overlap of genes. It has also been stated that differential gene expression on transcript level matches protein abundance to only about 40% (Tian *et al.*, 2004).

In the present study, system biomedicine framework was used to identify molecular biomarker signature and inform systemic drug targeting in non-small cell lung cancer (Fig. 1).

For this purpose, gene expression profiles from lung cancer were subjected to integrative analyses with genome-scale biomolecular networks to reveal molecular signature at mRNA, miRNA and protein levels, which serve as potential drug targets for therapeutics innovation. The differential expression profiles and the risk discrimination performance of the reporter biomolecules were cross-validated in independent transcriptome datasets.

Materials and methods

Gene Expression Profiling in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

For non-small cell lung cancer, the transcriptome data (GSE54712) was obtained from the previous study (Lopez *et al.*, 2014) through the publicly available Gene Expression Omnibus (NCBI-GEO) dataset (Barrett *et al.*, 2013), mRNA profiling was hybridized to in-situ oligonucleotide microarrays (Agilent-014850 Whole Human Genome Microarray 4x44K).

Differentially expressed gene

The gene expression data set was normalized for identifying DEGs through the Robust Multi-Array Average (RMA) expression measure and it was implemented in the “LIMMA” package of

Bioconductor platform. To control the false discovery rate in multiple-testing the p-values were adjusted by Benjamini Hochberg’s method and by using adjusted p-value >0.01 criterion was cutoff to designate statistical significance.

The hierarchical clustering analysis was applied to categorize patients and gene into groups using Heatmap3 package. All analyses packages were implemented in R (version 3.2.3), analysis were performed through the Bioconductor platform (Gentleman *et al.*, 2004).

Gene function enrichment

To find out molecular function, biological process and molecular pathway annotations of the identified DEGs through Database for Annotation, Visualization and Integrated Discovery (DAVID) (version v6.8) bioinformatics resources by using gene overrepresentation analyses. Whole set of genome annotation for human genome was used as the background reference set. Analyses were carried out by using Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathway database as the annotation sources. DAVID bioinformatics resources were used to find out molecular pathway annotations of the identified DEGs (Huang *et al.*, 2009). P-values were determined by using Fisher Exact test and Benjamini-Hochberg’s correction was used the multiple testing correction technique. Results with adjusted-p <0.01 were considered as statistically significant.

Analysis and Reconstruction of Protein-Protein Interaction Sub-network

The previously reconstructed protein-protein interaction (PPI) network of *Homo sapiens* (Karagoz *et al.*, 2016), which consist of 288,033 physical interactions between 21,052 proteins, was recruited in the present study to construct a PPI subnetwork around the protein encoded by the identified DEGs.

The subnetwork was shown as an undirected graph, where nodes represent the proteins and the edges represent the interactions between the proteins. The sub-network was visualized and analyzed via Cytoscape (v3.6.1).

To determine highly connected proteins (i.e., hub proteins) a topological analysis was applied through Cyto-Hubba plugin (Chin *et al.*, 2009) and the dual-metric approach considering degree and between’s centrality metrics simultaneously were employed (Calimlioglu *et al.*, 2015).

Determination of Reporter Transcription Factors and miRNAs

Transcriptional regulatory biomolecules (i.e. TFs) was obtained through human transcriptional regulation

interaction data bases TRRUST v2 (www.grnpedia.org/trrust) which significant changes has occurred at transcriptional level. To identify miRNAs around which significant changes occur at transcriptional level, the experimentally verified miRNA-target gene interactions was involved in this study which were obtained through human transcriptional regulation interaction (Bovolenta *et al.*, 2012) and miRTarbase (Release 6.0) (Chou *et al.*, 2016) as well as previous study (Gov *et al.*, 2017). To obtained z-score and corresponding p-values of the regulatory molecules, the reporter features algorithms (Patil and Nielsen, 2005) was used and implemented as described previously (Kori *et al.*, 2016). P-values were corrected via Benjamini-Hochberg's methods and statistically significant (adjusted $p < 0.01$) results were considered as reporter regulatory elements.

Cross-validation and Evaluation of Performance of Reporter Biomolecules

According to their prognostic index and survival multivariate the patients were divided into low and high-risk group and risk assessments were performed through oncolnc (Anaya, 2016).

The differences between the risk groups in gene expression levels were represented via box plots and statistical significance of the differences was estimated through t-test. Survival signatures of reporter biomolecules were evaluated through Kaplan-Meier plots and a log -rank p-value < 0.01 was considered as a cut-off to describe statistical significance in all survival analyses.

Identification of Candidate Drugs through Drug Repositioning

To identify novel therapeutics in NSCLC through drug repositioning the transcriptome guided drug repositioning tool and Drug Gene Interaction Database (dgidb) (Cotto *et al.*, 2017) was used to designate the candidate drugs targeting the hub protein and reporter TFs. Total 213 drugs and 7 proteins was found for non-small cell lung cancer through dgidb. Drugs associated with each disease dataset were expected by employing the

hypergeometric probability test. For exploring more accurate drug candidates for specific disease, it is suggested to search based on the particular condition (Turanli *et al.*, 2017).

Results

Genome Reprogramming in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

In this present study, statistical test LIMMA was used to identify DEGs from noise and outliers in the transcriptome dataset. The parametric method LIMMA was identified 380 DEGs with statistical significance of adjusted $p < 0.01$. Among those, 169 genes were up regulated, whereas 211 genes were down regulated (Fig. 2A). Through hierarchical clustering analysis based on the profiles of DEGs, it was shown that the tumor and normal sample were distinguished with 100% specificity and 92% sensitivity (Fig. 2B). These DEGs were considered in further analysis.

To clarify the molecular functions, biological processes, cellular components and KEGG pathways functional overrepresentation were carried out, which associated with proteins encoded by the DEGs. GO analysis was performed by DAVID results represent that both up regulated and down regulated DEGs are significantly enriched in biological processes (BP), where up regulated genes include regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction, regulation of Rho protein signal transduction, positive regulation of GTPase activity, small GTPase mediated signal transduction, positive regulation of GTPase activity, cell adhesion, regulation of heart rate by cardiac conduction (Table 1) and down regulated genes include negative regulation of endopeptidase activity, oxidation-reduction process, daunorubicin metabolic process, doxorubicin metabolic process, progesterone metabolic process (Table 1).

In case of cellular component (CC), up regulated genes are involved in plasma membrane extracellular region, integral component of plasma membrane, intercalated disc, cell junction, myosin complex (Table 1) and down regulated genes are involved in

integral component of plasma membrane, integral component of membrane, proteinaceous extracellular matrix (Table 1). In addition, up regulated genes were enriched in molecular function (MF) including guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity, Rho guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity, serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity, calmodulin binding, actin filament binding (Table 1) and down

regulated enriched in serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity, oxidoreductase activity, ketosteroid monooxygenase activity, trans-1,2-dihydrobenzene-1,2-diol dehydrogenase activity, phenanthrene 9,10-monooxygenase activity, chemorepellent activity, symporter activity, metallopeptidase activity (Table 1).

Table 1. Functional overrepresentation of differentially expressed genes in non-small cell lung cancer.

Gene Cluster	Category	Pathway	No. of gene	P-value	
Cluster 1 (Up Regulated Genes)	Gene Ontology Biological Process	Regulation of small GTPase mediated signal transduction	5	2.0E-2	
		regulation of Rho protein signal transduction	4	2.5E-2	
		positive regulation of GTPase activity	9	7.2E-2	
		small GTPase mediated signal transduction	6	4.3E-2	
		positive regulation of GTPase activity	9	7.2E-2	
		regulation of heart rate by cardiac conduction	3	3.0E-2	
	Gene Ontology Cellular Component	extracellular matrix organization	7	4.2E-3	
		cell adhesion	11	3.0E-3	
		plasma membrane	45	3.6E-3	
		extracellular region	19	4.5E-2	
		integral component of plasma membrane	18	2.9E-2	
		intercalated disc	4	4.3E-3	
	Gene Ontology Molecular Function	cell junction	9	1.9E-2	
		myosin complex	3	5.2E-2	
		guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	6	2.1E-3	
		Rho guanyl-nucleotide exchange factor activity	4	2.1E-2	
		serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity	4	3.8E-2	
	KEGG Pathways	calmodulin binding	5	5.7E-2	
		actin filament binding	4	8.1E-2	
		motor activity	3	9.1E-2	
		ECM-receptor interaction	3	1.6E-1	
	Cluster 2 (Down Regulated Genes)	Gene Ontology Biological Process	Focal adhesion	4	2.3E-1
			PI3K-Akt signaling pathway	4	5.4E-1
			negative regulation of endopeptidase activity	8	3.3E-4
			oxidation-reduction process	15	4.7E-3
			cellular response to jasmonic acid stimulus	3	6.8E-4
Gene Ontology Cellular Component		daunorubicin metabolic process	3	3.1E-3	
		doxorubicin metabolic process	3	3.1E-3	
		progesterone metabolic process	3	3.9E-3	
		plasma membrane	63	4.3E-4	
		integral component of plasma membrane	26	4.7E-3	
		integral component of membrane	70	4.9E-3	
		proteinaceous extracellular matrix	7	5.6E-2	
		serine-type endopeptidase inhibitor activity	7	5.2E-4	
		oxidoreductase activity	10	2.4E-4	
		Gene Ontology Molecular Function	ketosteroid monooxygenase activity	3	3.2E-4
trans-1,2-dihydrobenzene-1,2-diol dehydrogenase activity	3		6.3E-4		
phenanthrene 9,10-monooxygenase activity	3		6.3E-4		
chemorepellent activity	3		3.2E-2		
symporter activity	4		1.6E-2		
metallopeptidase activity	4		5.2E-2		
Phosphatidylinositol signaling system	6		8.0E-3		
Pathways in cancer	9		1.3E-1		
KEGG Pathways	PI3K-Akt signaling pathway	6	4.5E-1		
	Regulation of actin cytoskeleton	4	5.1E-1		

The up regulated DEGs and down regulated DEGs both are significantly enriched which are analyzed in KEGG pathway analysis.

The results are represented up regulation of pathways in ECM-receptor interaction, focal adhesion and

PI3K-Akt signaling pathway. On the other hand, down regulated DEGs were enriched in Phosphatidylinositol signaling system, Pathways in cancer, PI3K-Akt signaling pathway and regulation of actin cytoskeleton pathways which were represent in non-small cell lung cancer (Table 1).

Table 2. Reporter biomolecules are in non-small cell lung cancer. Statistically significant ($p < 0.01$) values are given in bold and italic.

Symbol	Description	Feature	Hazard ratio (TCGA)
PTPN20	Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase, Non-Receptor Type 20	Hub Protein	NA
ST6GALNAC2	ST6 N-Acetylgalactosaminide Alpha-2,6-Sialyltransferase 2	Hub Protein	1.12
ELMO1	Engulfment And Cell Motility 1	Hub Protein	1.59
TXLNGY	Taxilin Gamma Pseudogene, Y-Linked	Hub Protein	
NPR3	Natriuretic Peptide Receptor 3	Hub Protein	1.03
CFH	Complement Factor H	Hub Protein	1.05
CNTNAP3B	Contactin Associated Protein Like 3B	Hub Protein	NA
CKMT1A	Creatine Kinase, Mitochondrial 1A	Hub Protein	1.21
TP53	tumor protein p53	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.02
SP3	SP3 transcription factor	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.08
JUN	JUN proto-oncogene	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.08
PPARG	Peroxisome proliferator- activated receptor gamma	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.23
TFAP2A	Transcription factor AP-2 alpha	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.68
TWIST1	Twist basic helix-loop-helix transcription factor 1	Reporter Transcription Factor	1.25
miR-146a-5p	MicoRNA-146a	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-210-3p	MICroRNA-210	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-374a-5p	MICroRNA-374a	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-548b-3p	MICroRNA-548b	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-544a	MICroRNA-544a	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-152-3p	MICroRNA-152	Receptor mirRNA	NA
miR-204-5p	MICroRNA-204	Receptor mirRNA	NA
All Hubs	PTPN20, ST6GALNAC2, ELMO1, TXLNGY, NPR3, CFH, CNTNAP3B, CKMT1A	All Hub Proteins	1.51
All TFs	TP53, SP3, JUN, PPARG, TFAP2A, TWIST1	All receptor transcription factors	1.65

Proteomic Signatures in Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer

Central proteins, so called “hub proteins” have a significant role in signal transduction events during disease progression.

To identify these hub proteins a PPI sub-network was constructed around proteins encoded by the DEGs via their physical interactions and topological analysis was formed.

As a result, eight hub proteins were found (Table 2) and those are Protein Tyrosine Phosphatase, Non-Receptor Type 20 (PTPN20), ST6 N-

Acetylgalactosaminide Alpha-2,6-Sialyltransferase 2 (ST6GALNAC2), Engulfment And Cell Motility 1 (ELMO1), Taxilin Gamma Pseudogene, Y-Linked (TXLNGY), Natriuretic Peptide Receptor 3 (NPR3), Complement Factor H (CFH), Contactin Associated Protein Like 3B (CNTNAP3B), Creatine Kinase U-type and mitochondria (CKMT1A).

The transcriptional and post-transcriptional regulatory components (i.e., TFs and miRNAs) occurs significant changes at transcriptional level, which were also identified. The results have found six TFs and seven miRNAs as reporter transcriptional regulatory components (Table 2).

Table 3. Selected repositioned drugs in non-small cell lung cancer.

Repositioning drug	Drug Class/ Status/ Description
Docetaxel	Approved, Investigational. Docetaxel is a clinically well-established anti-mitotic chemotherapy medication used mainly for the treatment of breast, ovarian, and non-small cell lung cancer. Docetaxel reversibly binds to tubulin with high affinity in a 1:1 stoichiometric ratio.
Gemcitabine	Approved, Gemcitabine is used in various carcinomas: non-small cell lung cancer, pancreatic cancer, bladder cancer and breast cancer. It is being investigated for use in oesophageal cancer, and is used experimentally in lymphomas and various other tumor types.
Carboplatin	Approved an organoplatinum compound that possesses antineoplastic activity.
Paclitaxel	An organoplatinum compound that possesses antineoplastic activity. It is available as an intravenous solution for injection and the newer formulation contains albumin-bound paclitaxel marketed under the brand name Abraxane.
Crizotinib	Crizotinib an inhibitor of receptor tyrosine kinase for the treatment of non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC). Verification of the presence of ALK fusion gene is done by Abbott Molecular's Vysis ALK Break Apart FISH Probe Kit. This verification is used to select for patients suitable for treatment. FDA approved in August 26, 2011.
Bevacizumab	A recombinant humanized monoclonal IgG1 antibody that binds to and inhibits the biologic activity of human vascular endothelial growth factor (VEGF). Bevacizumab contains human framework regions and the complementarity-determining regions of a murine antibody that binds to VEGF.
Gemcitabine	Gemcitabine is used in various carcinomas: non-small cell lung cancer, pancreatic cancer, bladder cancer and breast cancer. It is being investigated for use in oesophageal cancer, and is used experimentally in lymphomas and various other tumor types.

Cross-validation and Risk Discrimination Performance of Reporter Biomolecules

The differential expression signatures was validated and the analysis of the risk discrimination performance of reporter biomolecules (i.e., 8 hub proteins, 6 TFs and 7miRNAs) were performed using independent RNA-seq and miRNA-seq dataset obtained from TCGA. According to the expression levels of the reporter biomolecules, the samples were divided into two groups and groups are entitled as low-risk and high-risk considering their risk discrimination performance. The differences in the gene expression levels (encoding hub proteins or reporter TFs) between the risk groups were presented via box-plots and prognostic capabilities based on survival data were analyzed Kaplan-Meier plots, log-rank test and hazard ratio (Figs 3 and 4). Furthermore, the discrimination power of the all hub proteins and all reporter TFs were also analyzed and

statistically significant performance in terms of survival probabilities in all datasets were found in both groups.

Identification of Candidate Drugs through Drug Repositioning

Considering hub proteins and transcription factors as potential drug targets and the transcriptomic signatures of genes within the disease-gene-drug triad we identified potential drug for each target protein using the transcriptome guided drug repositioning tool and the Drug Gene Interaction Database (dgidb). As a result 213 drugs and 7 proteins was found (Fig. 5).

Among these identified drugs seven drugs is used for non-small cell lung cancer which is approved by National Cancer Institute. Gemcitabine, Carboplatin, paclitaxel, Docetaxel, Crizotinib, Bevacizumab and

Gemcitabine drugs are used for the treatment of NSCLC (Table 3).

Discussion

Although the prevalence and mortality of NSCLC are among the highest worldwide and the disease has been studied extensively, there is still a need for more accurate prognostic and diagnostic markers as well as for information about the underlying molecular events in the disease's development. In the present

study, we followed a multi-omics data integration framework to reveal molecular signatures at mRNA, miRNA and protein levels, which offers the promise as biomarkers and potential drug targets for efficacious treatments. In the gene expression study, we performed several analyses of NSCLC, including GO, clustering, new biomarker discovery, a comparison of survival based on histology and gene expression profiles, and analysis of patient survival.

Fig. 1. The methodology of multi-stage analysis which is employed in the present study. (A) Gene expression data were obtained from the Gene Expression Omnibus (GEO) database. The dataset was statistically analyzed to identify differentially expressed genes (DEGs). (B) Functional enrichment of DEGs was performed to identify significantly enriched Gene Ontology (GO) terms and Pathways. (C) Protein-protein interaction network was reconstructed around DEGs and the topological analyses were performed via Cytoscape to identify hub proteins. (D) To identify reporter micro-RNA (miRNA) and transcription factors (TFs), DEGs were integrated with miRNA-target gene and TF-target interactions and the statistically significant miRNAs and TFs were considered as the reporter transcriptional regulatory elements. (E) The survival analysis of the hub biomolecules was done through The Cancer Genome Atlas (TCGA) NSCLC datasets via SurvExpress and Oncolnc. (F) The candidate drug molecules were identified by Drug Gene Interaction Database (dgiddb).

The analysis of gene expression profiles in lung cancer samples resulted with a total of 380 DEGs with statistically significant changes in their expression profiles. Overrepresentation analyses for DEGs

indicated the prominence of ECM organization and associated cell communication/signaling pathways (such as focal adhesion, ECM-receptor interaction pathways, and PI3K-Akt signaling pathway); hence,

emphasized the critical roles of tumor microenvironment in NSCLC. Recent studies indicated the importance of tumor microenvironment as a decisive factor in tumorigenesis in various cancers (Dzobo *et al.*, 2016, Gollapalli *et al.*, 2017, Gov *et al.*, 2017, Hu *et al.*, 2017, Miskolczi *et al.*, 2018). GO analysis of statistically significant up regulated genes in NSCLC uncovered biological

processes involved in cell adhesion and positive regulation of GTPase activity, whereas GO analysis of statistically significant down regulated genes in NSCLC uncovered genes involved in much more diverse processes, such as anatomical structure development, oxidation-reduction process and negative regulation of endopeptidase activity.

Fig. 2. (A & B): Heat map of differentially expressed genes and clustering analysis of DEGs. The above of the heat map presents clustering of samples and the left of the heat map presents clustering of the DEGs. Purple: high expression level and Green: low expression level. (A) Showed the hierarchical clustering (B) represent the clustering of samples/ patients.

Therefore, in the last decades, the reconstruction of accurate PPI sub-networks gained importance with the emergence of systems medicine and systems pharmacology concepts, which aim to offer solutions to many emerging problems associated with diseases such as identifying efficacious biomarkers and therapeutic targets for accurate diagnosis, prognosis, and therapeutics (Sevimoglu and Arga, 2014, Turanli and Arga, 2017). We reconstructed a PPI sub-network around the DEGs in NSCLC, and analyzed the topology of the reconstructed network to identify central proteins, i.e. hub proteins, that have the potential to contribute to the initiation and/or progression of cancer development. The regulation of

gene expression is controlled by TFs and miRNAs at transcriptional and/or post-transcriptional levels; thus changes in these molecules may provide crucial information on dysregulation of gene expression in NSCLC. Therefore, reporter TFs and miRNAs have been identified.

The role of systems outlook gradually increases through improving existent approaches and developing novel concepts to provide possible solutions to the grand challenge in pharmacology, i.e., the development of efficacious treatment strategies for tackling the complexities of the diseases (Turanli and Arga, 2017).

Fig. 3. Cross validation and prognostic performance analyses of hub proteins. (A) Kaplan-Meier plots representing the prognostic power of all hub proteins in NSCLC. (B) Box-plots present differential expression of genes encoding hub proteins in two risk groups.

Fig. 4. Cross validation and prognostic performance analyses of Transcriptional Factors. (A) Kaplan-Meier plots representing the prognostic power of all TFs in NSCLC. (B) Box-plots present differential expression of genes encoding TFs in two risk groups.

The development of novel and effective treatment strategies for complex pathophysiology's, such as cancers, requires an understanding of the generation and progression mechanisms. Besides, systems biology research generates new information that can help in understanding the mechanisms behind disease pathogenesis to identify new biomarkers and therapeutic targets and to enable drug discovery. By using molecular signatures 213 drugs and seven

proteins was identified. Among these drugs seven drugs is used for NSCLC which is approved by national cancer institute.

Integration of transcriptome datasets with biological network models provides molecular signatures, which will be beneficial for understanding etiopathogenesis and biological mechanisms of the diseases, and for developing effective and safe medications.

Fig. 5. Identified potential drugs for molecular signature by using the transcriptome guided drug repositioning tool and dgidd.

Conclusion

In this present study, transcriptome data were integrated with genome-scale biological networks to reveal molecular signatures at RNA and protein levels.

Analysis of the genome reprogramming in NSCLC emphasized the decisive role of tumor microenvironment in tumorigenesis. Eight protein, six TFs and seven miRNA came into prominence as potential drug targets. The differential expression profile of these reporter biomolecules were cross validated in independent RNA-seq and miRNA-seq datasets. Moreover, seven novel candidate drugs were identified for NSCLC which is approved by national cancer institute.

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Declaration

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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